

Simulating Nanofluidics: an LLM Study

Aman Chawla

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Abstract

In this note the authors present results that show the magnetic field and its power spectrum generated by a box of N particles with random velocities and a drift. The simulation is intended to mimic a chunk of fluid in motion, with the goal of determining its velocity using an NV center (Nitrogen Vacancy) which can sense the magnetic field. We also provide simulations of the flow generated by an initial quantum pump.

In the paper [1], the authors present molecular dynamics simulations to mimic fluid flow and then sense the flow using an NV center via the magnetic field generated. Their analysis shows that the power spectrum of the measured magnetic field is related to the drift velocity of the fluid. In this note, we use an LLM to present us with a Python script (Algorithm 1-2) and simulation results (Figures 1 and 2) for this setting.

In future work, we will provide a specific bounding box shape and study flow in it using similar methodology. Our goal is ultimately to develop a nanopump that can generate nanoflows which can then be sensed using the mechanism simulated in this note. Next, we present initial simulation results of a quantum pump. The pump utilizes ion flow in solution due to a weak electric field followed by a selectivity filter that only lets the ions out. We use a Python script (Algorithm 3) to plot the evolution of the wavefunction of the output ions with time (Figures 3 and 4).

In future work, we hope to combine the quantum pump and the quantum sensor to simulate a full-fledged quantum flow control setup.

References

- [1] Daniel Cohen, Ramil Nigmatullin, Oded Kenneth, Fedor Jelezko, Maxim Khodas, and Alex Retzker. Utilising nv based quantum sensing for velocimetry at the nanoscale. *Scientific Reports*, 10(1):5298, 2020.

Algorithm 1 Python molecular dynamics.

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.fft import fft, fftfreq
# Constants and parameters
N = 30 # number of particles
L = 10.0 # size of the simulation box (cubic box with length L)
d = 2.0 # distance of NV center below the box (along z-axis)
mass = 1.0 # mass of particles (assuming uniform)
dt = 0.01 # time step for the simulation
n_steps = 100 # number of simulation steps
epsilon = 1.0 # Lennard-Jones potential parameter (depth of potential well)
sigma = 1.0 # Lennard-Jones potential parameter (finite distance at which inter
# Initialize particle positions and velocities
positions = np.random.rand(N, 3) * L
# positions in a 3D box (x, y, z)
velocities = np.random.randn(N, 3) * 0.1
# random initial velocities
# NV center position (below the box, center of x-y projection)
nv_center = np.array([L / 2, L / 2, -d])
# Define the Lennard-Jones potential
def lennard_jones(r, epsilon, sigma):
    return 4 * epsilon * ((sigma / r)**12 - (sigma / r)**6)
# Compute forces using the Lennard-Jones potential
def compute_forces(positions, epsilon, sigma, L):
    forces = np.zeros_like(positions)
    for i in range(N):
        for j in range(i + 1, N):
            rij = positions[i] - positions[j]
# Apply minimum image convention for periodic boundary conditions
            rij = rij - np.round(rij / L) * L
            r = np.linalg.norm(rij)
            if r > 0: # To avoid division by zero
                f = 24 * epsilon * (2 * (sigma / r)**12 - (sigma
                    forces[i] += f
                    forces[j] -= f

    return forces
```

Algorithm 2 Part 2 of the simulation algorithm.

```
# Compute magnetic field at NV center due to moving particles (Biot–Savart Law)
def compute_magnetic_field(positions, velocities, nv_center):
    mu_0 = 1.0 # permeability of free space (simplified for units)
    magnetic_field = np.zeros(3)
    for i in range(N):
        r = nv_center - positions[i]
        r_mag = np.linalg.norm(r)
        if r_mag > 0: # avoid division by zero
            cross_product = np.cross(velocities[i], r)
            magnetic_field += mu_0 * cross_product / (r_mag**3)
    return magnetic_field
# Main simulation loop
magnetic_fields = []
for step in range(n_steps):
    # Update forces
    forces = compute_forces(positions, epsilon, sigma, L)
# Update velocities and positions using Velocity Verlet algorithm
    velocities += forces * dt / (2 * mass)
    positions += velocities * dt
    velocities += forces * dt / (2 * mass)
# Apply periodic boundary conditions
    positions = np.mod(positions, L)
# Compute magnetic field at NV center
    magnetic_field = compute_magnetic_field(positions, velocities, nv_center)
    magnetic_fields.append(magnetic_field)
# Convert magnetic field list to numpy array for further analysis
magnetic_fields = np.array(magnetic_fields)
# Compute the magnitude of the magnetic field over time
magnetic_magnitude = np.linalg.norm(magnetic_fields, axis=1)
# Plot the magnetic field magnitude over time plt.figure()
plt.plot(magnetic_magnitude) plt.xlabel('Time step') plt.ylabel('Magnetic field m
# Compute and plot the power spectrum (Fourier Transform of the magnetic field m
magnetic_spectrum = fft(magnetic_magnitude)
freqs = fftfreq(n_steps, dt)
plt.figure()
plt.plot(freqs[:n_steps // 2], np.abs(magnetic_spectrum)[:n_steps // 2])
plt.xlabel('Frequency')
plt.ylabel('Power Spectrum (Magnetic Field)')
plt.title('Power Spectrum of Magnetic Field at NV Center') plt.show()
```

Figure 1: Variation of the sensed magnetic field with time. The vertical axis is magnetic field magnitude in unitless form.

Figure 2: Power spectrum of the magnetic field at the NV center. The horizontal axis is frequency in unitless form.

Algorithm 3 Script to generate ion flow.

```
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from scipy.sparse import diags
from scipy.sparse.linalg import splu
# Constants
hbar = 1.0545718e-34
# Reduced Planck's constant (J·s)
m = 1.6726219e-27 # Mass of ion (kg) (Assume proton for simplicity)
e = 1.60217662e-19 # Elementary charge (C)
L = 1e-9 # Length of the simulation box (m)
Nx = 1000 # Number of spatial points
dx = L / (Nx - 1) # Spatial step size
dt = 1e-18 # Time step (s)
V0 = 50e-10 # Strength of weak electric potential (J) total_time = 10
# Total simulation time (s)
# Create spatial grid
x = np.linspace(0, L, Nx)
# Initialize wavefunction as a Gaussian centered at x = L/2
def initial_wavefunction(x):
    x0 = L / 2 # Center position of the wavepacket
    sigma = L / 20 # Width of the wavepacket
    k0 = 5e10 # Initial momentum (magnitude)
    return np.exp(-(x - x0)**2 / (2 * sigma**2)) * np.exp(1j * k0 * x)
psi = initial_wavefunction(x)
# Normalize the wavefunction
def normalize(psi, dx):
    return psi / np.sqrt(np.sum(np.abs(psi)**2) * dx)
psi = normalize(psi, dx)
# Potential energy: linear electric potential
V = V0 * (x - L / 2)
# Construct the Hamiltonian matrix (discretized in space)
def hamiltonian_matrix(Nx, dx, V, hbar, m):
    diagonal = np.ones(Nx) * (-2.0)
    off_diagonal = np.ones(Nx - 1)
    # Kinetic energy operator (Laplacian)
    T = diags([off_diagonal, diagonal, off_diagonal], [-1, 0, 1]) / (dx**2)
    # Add the potential energy (diagonal part)
    U = diags(V) # Hamiltonian
    H = -( / 2m) * Laplacian + V(x)
    H = -(hbar**2 / (2 * m)) * T + U
    return H
H = hamiltonian_matrix(Nx, dx, V, hbar, m)
# Crank-Nicolson method matrices: (I + i H dt / 2) and (I - i H dt / 2)
I = diags([np.ones(Nx)], [0])
A = (I + 1j * dt / (2 * hbar) * H).tocsc()
B = (I - 1j * dt / (2 * hbar) * H).tocsc()
# Precompute the LU decomposition of A for efficient solving A_lu = splu(A)
# Time evolution loop
n_steps = int(total_time / dt)
psi_list = [psi]
for step in range(n_steps): # Solve the linear system: A * psi_next = B * psi
    psi = A_lu.solve(B @ psi) # Normalize the wavefunction after each step
    psi = normalize(psi, dx) # Save wavefunction at intervals
    if step % 100 == 0:
```

Figure 3: Quantum flow under weak electric field.

Figure 4: Quantum flow under relatively stronger electric field.